

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Measuring Polymer Melts Under High-Pressure Conditions

This Application Highlight addresses the use of C-Therm's novel HT-TLS300 sensor for testing polymer melts under varying pressure conditions up to 3000 psi.

Polymer melts are widely used in various industries, such as plastics, rubber, and coatings, for their unique properties and processing advantages. However, the thermal conductivity of polymer melts is poorly understood, and it can vary significantly depending on the polymer's temperature, pressure, and molecular structure. In addition, many analysis methods struggle with testing this material type due to sample test condition requirements and the potential for sensor damage that may occur under said conditions. Therefore, there is a need for a robust, reliable and accurate method to measure the thermal conductivity of polymer melts under different conditions, which can help optimize the processing parameters and improve product quality and performance.

The TLS method is well-suited to testing polymer melts' thermal conductivity. The sensor consists of a thin metal wire sheathed in stainless steel that acts as both a heat source and a temperature sensor. C-Therm has developed novel capabilities with the TLS around temperature and pressure testing, allowing for representative data collection above what is typically offered in the industry. Herein, we describe the use of C-Therm's HT-TLS300 for testing a Polystyrene (PS) melt at 275°C under varying pressures up to 3000 psi.

Figure 1: C-Therm's HT-TLS300 Pressure Cell.

The TLS sensor was used to measure the thermal conductivity of polystyrene, a common thermoplastic polymer. Polystyrene was chosen as a representative polymer melt because it has a well-defined melting point (around 275°C) and a relatively low viscosity. The sensor was calibrated with a reference material (Macor) at room temperature and then inserted into a stainless steel pressure cell containing the polystyrene pellets. The pressure cell was connected to a remote pressurization system that used nitrogen gas to apply pressures up to 3000 psi. The pressure cell was also placed inside a thermal furnace that controlled the temperature of the sample. The sensor measured the thermal conductivity of polystyrene at four different pressures (14.7, 500, 1500, and 3000 psi) and at the same temperature (275°C). The results are shown in Figure 2, along with the literature values and the expected trends.

Figure 2: Thermal Conductivity of PS at 275°C Under Varying Pressures.

As can be seen from Figure 2, the sensor captured the increase in polystyrene's thermal conductivity as a function of pressure, as predicted by the literature. The measured values were also within the error range of the sensor specifications and showed good repeatability and consistency. The sensor demonstrated its ability to measure the thermal conductivity of polymer melts under pressure and at elevated temperatures with high accuracy and precision. These results are also summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Summary of Results

Pressure (psi)	Measured k ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	Reference k ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	Bias
14.7 (Atmospheric)	0.194	0.183	5.90%
500	0.194	0.184	5.22%
1500	0.198	0.187	6.10%
3000	0.202	0.191	5.86%

The increase in polystyrene's thermal conductivity with pressure can be explained by the reduction in the free volume and molecular mobility of the polymer chains, which enhances the heat transfer efficiency. However, the effect of pressure is relatively small unless very high pressures (in the order of tens of megapascals) are applied. Therefore, the sensor can be used to measure the thermal conductivity of polymer melts under moderate pressures, which are more relevant for industrial applications.

The TLS sensor is a powerful tool that can measure the thermal conductivity of polymer melts under pressure and at elevated temperatures. The results showed good agreement with the literature values and the expected trends. The sensor can be used for applications that require accurate and reliable thermal conductivity data of polymer melts under different processing conditions. The sensor can also be applied to other types of polymer melts, such as polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyvinyl chloride, and to other materials that undergo phase transitions.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com